

APPLICATION OF HAMMICK AND ANDREW'S MIXTURE LAW FOR SOLUTES IN WATER

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It is shown that though mixture law is applicable to parachor of liquid-liquid mixtures, very low results are obtained when a solid solute is used. This has been supported by Hammick and Andrew's work and by the work of S. K. Ray, although they themselves have failed to observe this. In case of liquid mixtures, when water is one of the constituents, acetic acid shows normal behaviour and P_x can still be calculated in case of ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol and acetone by extrapolation ($x=1$).

Hammick and Andrew (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 754) showed that mixture law may be applied to determine the value of parachor of a solute in a solvent. They selected liquid mixtures and established that for non-associated solutes in non-associated solvents the values obtained for the parachor from the measurements on solutions are in excellent agreement with those found for the pure liquids. Associated solutes also showed an excellent agreement both in non-associated and associated solvents. They have concluded that the mixture method can be used by extrapolation to determine the parachors of liquid solutes even if the simple mixture law does not apply.

However, the work of Hammick and Andrew (*loc. cit.*) is limited to liquid mixtures only and in all cases organic solvents have been used. Hammick and Andrew (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 33) have applied the mixture law in one case to a mixture containing a solid and a liquid and have observed that the results in solution are lower by 30 units. Following are their results.

TABLE I

Tetranitromethane in benzene at 25.6°.

x	d_{4}^{25}	r_s	M_m	P_m	P_x
0.0	0.8737	28.23	78.05	206.0	—
0.3377	1.169	27.49	117.95	231.1	280.4
0.5032	1.302	27.70	138.0	243.2	279.1
0.6736	1.419	28.19	157.5	255.8	282.0
0.8561	1.540	28.92	179.0	269.6	280.3

$P(\text{calc.}) = 301.2$ Mean $P_x = 280.0$

The work has been extended by Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 671; 1935, 12, 248) and he finds that the mixture law (simple and straight line) is applicable in case of solutions of solids in liquids. Ray's results (*loc. cit.*) are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

Solvents.	Solutes.	Variation of x .	Variation of P_x .
Benzene	Naphthalene	0.331-0.095	312.6-310.7
CCl ₄	"	0.037-0.109	312.3-310.2
Chloroform	"	0.034-0.071	338.1-334.7
Pyridine	"	0.029-0.049	335.4-334.6
Benzene	8-Oxyquinoline	0.018-0.046	320.3-322.8
Nitrobenzene	Anthracene	0.010-0.011	419.1-416.5

In spite of these results Ray concludes that the parachor obeys straight line mixture law in dilute solutions. It will be observed that ' x ' varies from $M/100$ to $M/10$ in extreme cases. The sudgen's method of calculating parachor admits an error to the extent of 0.5% to 1%. This percentage of error is therefore possible in P_m . Hence, when P_x is calculated by the mixture law,

$$P_m = xP_x + (1-x) P_s$$

and the concentration varies from $M/100$ to $M/10$, the error may get magnified 100 to 10 times. Thus, the variation observed by Ray at such dilutions cannot be due to the applicability of the straight line mixture law. Moreover, in many cases the variation is not proportional to the concentration of the solute, and in some cases the parachor value falls instead of increasing as the concentration of the solute is increased. A comparison of his mean observed results and the calculated results is interesting and is shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Solvent.	Solute.	P_{mean} .	P_{calc} .	Solvent.	Solute.	P_{mean} .	P_{calc} .
Benzene	Naphthalene	311.8	313	Benzene	8-Quinoline	322.0	323.6
CCl ₄	"	311.6	"	CCl ₄	"	315.0	"
Chloroform	"	335.4	"	Chloroform	Xanthene	420.8	420.0
Pyridine	Naphthol	334.5	333	Pyridine	"	421.8	"
Ethyl acetate	"	322.0	"	Benzene	Phenanthrene	417.2	418.0
Benzene	Coumarin	311.0	314	CCl ₄	"	467.1	"
Chloroform	"	323.7	"	Acetone	"	361.0	"
Pyridine	"	318.0	"	Nitrobenzene	Anthracene	417.8	418.0

These results clearly show that in organic solvents the solute obeys the simple mixture law, although the results in pyridine are at variance due to the fact that pyridine does not behave as 'normal solvent'. We do not understand how Ray has come to the conclusion that the straight line mixture law is applicable. The variation between the mean results and the calculated results is about 0.5%, and hence the difference is within

the experimental error. In a series of papers published from our laboratories (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 225, 149, 153, 492; 1944, 21, 54, 61, 180, 386; 1945, 23, 52, 111, 114, 116, 312) we have shown that when a solid is dissolved in a solvent the observed values in general are smaller than the calculated values, and that there is no relation between concentration and P_{obs} . *e. g.* the straight line mixture law does not hold. Thus, the observations of Hammick and Andrew in case of liquid-liquid mixtures are not borne out in case of solid-liquid mixtures. In cases where the solvent is water, this deviation is more marked. Further, if the solid is an electrolyte and the solvent is water, the deviation from the mixture law is the greatest. Hammick and Andrew (*loc. cit.*) state that in water anomalous results are obtained, but they have done no work. Following table shows our results.

TABLE IV

Temp. = 25°.

Acetic acid in ethyl acetate.					Methyl alcohol in water.				
Conc.	<i>d.</i>	<i>r.</i>	P_m .	P_x .	Conc.	<i>d.</i>	<i>r.</i>	P_m .	P_x .
0.6613	0.9757	25.35	159.8	131.3	0.1980	0.9479	43.20	56.18	75.75
0.7577	0.9943	25.58	151.5	131.2	0.3761	0.9120	36.35	62.60	79.40
0.8204	1.007	25.70	145.5	131.2	0.5306	0.8784	31.01	68.28	82.40
0.8672	1.015	26.30	142.9	131.8	0.7305	0.8403	27.40	76.85	85.96
					1.0000	0.7931	23.65	—	88.95
Ethyl alcohol in water.					Acetic acid in water.				
0.1995	0.9305	31.07	59.87	90.22	0.2176	1.049	40.06	65.12	111.8
0.2370	0.9219	30.92	64.45	102.80	0.3427	1.059	36.96	75.39	119.8
0.5542	0.8504	26.33	89.30	119.10	0.6591	1.063	30.98	101.8	126.8
0.6697	0.8324	25.54	99.28	122.50	0.8154	1.058	29.38	114.9	129.0
0.8377	0.8098	24.35	113.70	125.60	1.0000	1.051	27.10	—	130.4
1.0000	0.7894	22.50	—	127.10					

According to Hammick and Andrew (*loc. cit.*), associated solutes give parachor values by the solution method both in non-associated solvents and associated solvents which are in excellent agreement with those observed for the pure liquid at the same temperature. Our results with acetic acid in ethyl acetate support these observations. In case of methyl and ethyl alcohols and acetic acid in water, the simple mixture law is not applicable, but the variation in the value of P_x with concentration indicates that the parachor of the solute can still be calculated by extrapolation ($x=1$). The results in water therefore are not anomalous as predicated by Hammick and Andrew (*loc. cit.*).

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Received April 19, 1948.

